

Advanced machine learning techniques for State-of-Health estimation in lithium-ion batteries: A comparative study

Marek Sedlařík^{a,*}, Petr Vyroubal^a, Dominika Capková^{a,b}, Edin Omerdic^c, Mitchell Rae^d, Martin Mačák^e, Martin Šedina^a, Tomáš Kazda^a

^a Department of Electrical and Electronic Technology, Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Communication, Brno University of Technology, Technická 10, 616 00, Brno, Czech Republic

^b Department of Chemical Sciences, Bernal Institute, University of Limerick, V94 T9PX, Limerick, Ireland

^c Department of Electronic and Computer Engineering, University of Limerick, V94 T9PX Limerick, Ireland

^d Department of Mathematics and Statistics, University of Limerick, V94 T9PX, Limerick, Ireland

^e Electric Vehicle Technologies, Transport Technologies, AIT Austrian Institute of Technology GmbH, Giefingasse 2, 1210 Vienna, Austria

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

State-of-Health
Li-ion battery
Machine learning
Support vector regression
Gaussian process regression
Feed-forward neural network
Adaptive neuro-fuzzy inference system

ABSTRACT

The accurate modeling and prediction of the State-of-Health (SOH) of lithium-ion (Li-ion) batteries are crucial for extending their lifespan, ensuring reliability, and minimizing the costs associated with extensive laboratory testing. This paper investigates the SOH estimation of Li-ion batteries utilizing advanced machine learning (ML) techniques. Specifically, 600 cycles were performed on Samsung INR18650–35E cells using the Constant Current Constant Voltage (CCCV) protocol. The input data for the ML methods were extracted from both charging and discharging cycles to achieve the best possible results.

Data-driven models with different methodological foundations were used to predict SOH: Gaussian Process Regression (GPR), Support Vector Regression (SVR), and from the field of Artificial Neural Networks (ANN), Feed-Forward Neural Network (FFNN) and Adaptive Neuro-Fuzzy Inference System (ANFIS), which utilizes fuzzy logic. The input features for the ML methods were analyzed using Pearson Correlation Analysis (PCA), and additional inputs for the ANFIS method were selected using Exhaustive Search (ES) to identify the optimal combination of inputs with the lowest Root Mean Square Error (RMSE). The individual ML methods were evaluated on datasets of various sizes using the features with the highest correlation to SOH and the full set of features to detect overfitting. Further experiments explored the dependency of RMSE on the amount of training data, and SOH estimation of one battery was performed using training data from another. Overall, experiments show that nearly all methods achieved RMSE below 0.5% for SOH estimation, with SVR proving the most stable technique and ANFIS excelling with meticulously optimized configurations.

1. Introduction

Lithium-ion (Li-ion) batteries undergo degradation caused by complex physical and chemical processes that affect all components of the Li-ion battery: electrodes, electrolyte, separator, and current collectors. Degradation is caused by calendar aging of the battery and cycling, with the overall effect resulting in performance loss, increased internal resistance, and especially in a reduction of total capacity [1,2]. Battery aging and degradation mechanisms can be significantly affected by critical stress factors such as fast charging at high currents, storing the battery outside the recommended temperature range, or operating the

battery with a high Depth-of-Discharge (DOD). Each of these factors contributes to battery degradation in a slightly different way.

Degradation mechanisms are generally categorized into two main types [3]: Loss of Lithium Inventory (LLI), where lithium ions are lost due to parasitic reactions, such as the deposition of metallic lithium on the surface of the anode, known as lithium plating, and the decomposition reactions and growth of the Solid Electrolyte Interphase (SEI) that primarily occur between the electrolyte and the anode, but to a lesser extent may also involve the cathode. On the other hand, Loss of Active Material (LAM) occurs on the electrodes, which may become damaged due to particle cracking or loss of electrical contact. In the study by Ren

* Corresponding author at: Department of Electrical and Electronic Technology, Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Communication, Brno University of Technology, Technická 10, 616 00, Brno, Czech Republic.

E-mail address: Marek.Sedlarik@vut.cz (M. Sedlařík).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.electacta.2025.145988>

Received 24 January 2025; Received in revised form 24 February 2025; Accepted 5 March 2025

Available online 6 March 2025

0013-4686/© 2025 The Authors. Published by Elsevier Ltd. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

et al. [4], Li-ion batteries are subjected to both types of degradation, LLI and LAM, separately, using an accelerated aging protocol specifically designed to highlight the occurrence of these phenomena in Li-ion batteries.

These degradation mechanisms primarily lead to a reduction in battery capacity and overall performance characteristics, which can eventually result in critical issues and battery failure. This phenomenon is expressed by the parameter State-of-Health (SOH), which is defined as the ratio between the current maximum capacity of the battery Q_i and its nominal capacity Q_0 (see Eq. (1)), generally expressed in ampere-hours (Ah).

$$SOH = \frac{Q_i}{Q_0} \cdot 100 \% \quad (1)$$

A new battery should have a nominal capacity, meaning its SOH is 100 %. This value gradually decreases over time, through cycles, and also depending on the DOD, operating temperature and current magnitude. SOH also indicates whether a battery is suitable for a specific application, as the period between a new battery's SOH value and its End-of-Life (EOL), typically considered to be 70–80 % SOH, is referred to as the "First life" cycle of the battery. During this phase, the battery is primarily intended for applications requiring high performance and reliability. Reaching the EOL milestone does not necessarily mean the battery will be recycled; rather, it may no longer be suitable for uses such as electric mobility but still could be applied in stationary battery storage systems, where high performance demands are less critical. Generally, currents flowing through the battery are reduced, DOD is limited, and the system operates in a relatively isolated environment with many monitoring elements and a more advanced Battery Management System (BMS), which includes certain types of predictive maintenance models [5].

This research contributes to the field of SOH estimation by providing a rigorous comparative analysis of advanced Machine Learning (ML) techniques, systematically evaluating their performance across varying dataset conditions. It meticulously examines the influence of dataset size on model accuracy and stability, offering a detailed characterization of each model with a focus on its suitability for different applications. The study investigates Support Vector Regression (SVR), Gaussian Process Regression (GPR), Feed-Forward Neural Network (FFNN), and Adaptive Neuro-Fuzzy Inference System (ANFIS), assessing their robustness and sensitivity to training data availability. Additionally, this research conducts a comprehensive examination of overfitting risks, particularly in ANFIS, and introduces an optimized input selection methodology to enhance its generalization capability. A key contribution of this study is the cross-battery SOH estimation analysis, which evaluates the transferability of ML models to datasets obtained from different battery cells. These insights contribute to enhancing the accuracy of SOH estimation in battery monitoring systems, ultimately leading to greater reliability and operational stability of energy storage systems.

Numerous studies have explored this field, providing valuable insights into feature selection and ML approaches for SOH estimation. For instance, Hu et al. [6] investigated feature selection techniques and applied ML models to enhance SOH estimation. The study introduced a fusion-based approach that combined multiple selection methods to optimize the input feature set, demonstrating its effectiveness in improving predictive performance. However, while their approach refines feature selection, it does not systematically assess how different feature sets impact model generalization across dataset sizes, nor does it analyze overfitting risks in different learning architectures. Furthermore, Hu et al. [6] focuses on multiple datasets but does not explicitly evaluate the cross-battery generalization of ML models, a critical factor in ensuring robust SOH estimation across different battery chemistries. Similarly, Eleftheriadis et al. [7] lacked a detailed assessment of dataset variability, fine-tuning, and cross-validation, while Zheng et al. [8] introduced a joint SOC-SOH estimation framework but did not include ANFIS or a systematic evaluation of model generalization across battery

datasets.

To fill existing research gaps, this study conducts a systematic evaluation of predictive models, focusing on dataset variability, generalization capabilities, and robustness to overfitting. By incorporating both custom-measured and publicly available datasets, including a prismatic cell dataset for validation, this research provides a more comprehensive characterization of model behavior. The inclusion of cross-battery validation, ANFIS analysis, and fine-tuning techniques further enhances the reliability and transferability of SOH predictions, contributing to more effective battery health monitoring strategies.

1.1. State-of-Health estimation

SOH estimation is an essential part of ensuring the proper operation of battery storage systems, as well as their reliability and planned maintenance. Today, various electrochemical, empirical, or mathematical models exist for prediction. Electrochemical models describe battery behavior and the complex processes occurring during charging, discharging, and particle transport. One of the most prominent electrochemical models for Li-ion batteries is the Pseudo-2-Dimensional (P2D) model, as introduced by Newman et al., which builds on fundamental concepts of porous electrode behavior and concentrated solution dynamics [9]. Numerous studies have since built upon this model. For instance, Raj et al. [10] investigated the effects of various charging and discharging rates on Li-ion battery degradation, modeling SEI growth, lithium plating, and their interactions at different temperatures. Similarly, Han et al. [11] developed a computationally efficient method for solving the full-order P2D model, enabling accurate simulation of lithium plating during fast charging. Hashemzadeh et al. [12] modified the P2D model by creating a single-particle model, specifically designed to predict battery behavior under high C-rates with reduced computational demands compared to the full P2D model. The accuracy of electrochemical models is highly dependent on the composition and structure of the battery, requiring these parameters to be precisely defined. Furthermore, to ensure that computational models are both efficient and accurate, various optimizations are essential based on multiple studies [11,12].

In contrast, empirical models, especially those based solely on data, generate output purely based on the quality and scope of the input data. There is also a category of semi-empirical models, in which the battery is replaced by an Equivalent Circuit Model (ECM), with the dual polarization model being the most commonly used. Hentunen et al. [13] discuss a method for identifying parameters of the ECM model. Wang et al. [14] enhanced a first-order RC equivalent circuit model for Li-ion batteries through experimental parameter optimization and sensitivity analysis. In the study by Park et al. [15], a semi-empirical SOH model was proposed to capture electrochemical aging characteristics during cycling and short-term rest periods, enhancing degradation predictions. While these models are based on experimental measurements, they still describe the behavior of the battery.

Although electrochemical and ECM are widely used for modeling Li-ion batteries, this study focuses only on data-driven models, specifically ML. While these methods may not inherently offer the same level of accuracy, their precision can be significantly improved by selecting appropriate input features. The performance of these models depends not only on the type of data used but also on how the chosen method processes that data. Some methods are highly susceptible to overfitting, meaning even minor noise could critically impact their performance.

This study provides a comprehensive comparison of four distinct ML methods, each differing in methodology and computational complexity. This comparison offers valuable insights for model selection and optimization in specific applications. The objective is not only to assess estimation accuracy but also to analyze stability, sensitivity to dataset size, and compatibility across different batteries.

While dataset size can significantly influence model performance, potentially leading to overfitting or conversely determining the

minimum dataset size required to achieve sufficient accuracy, the selection of input features is especially crucial. Features susceptible to noise can degrade model performance, making certain methods unsuitable under specific conditions. To address this challenge, this study incorporates a precise analysis of input data and preprocessing, employing correlation analysis and exhaustive search to optimize feature selection.

The result of this research is a systematic evaluation of fundamentally different modeling approaches, defining their suitability under various conditions and constraints. By examining models that differ diametrically in methodology and computational demands, this research provides a structured perspective on their practical applicability, guiding the selection of the most appropriate technique for battery SOH estimation.

2. Machine learning methods

In recent years, data-driven models, particularly those using ML techniques, have shown great promise for SOH estimation. These techniques can detect various anomalies in experimentally measured data that would be difficult or impossible to analyze using other methods. ML uses algorithms and statistical models that allow the system to learn from the provided data and make predictions or decisions without direct programming interaction. By analyzing large volumes of experimental and computational data, ML algorithms can uncover hidden patterns and correlations that traditional methods could ignore. ML methods can be categorized from several perspectives, primarily in terms of the approach to training data [16]: Supervised Learning (SL) involves finding relationships between inputs and known outputs. Unsupervised Learning (UL) trains the model on unlabeled data, searching for hidden patterns and structures. Reinforcement Learning (RL) works on a feedback-based system, rewarding the model when it moves closer to the target and ignoring actions when it does the opposite. This method relies on trial and error to achieve the most optimal result.

Fig. 1 illustrates the categorization of ML methods in terms of probabilistic and deterministic approaches. There are many ML methods and their variations, but only the basic ML techniques that are most commonly used for SOH prediction are described below.

Probabilistic methods include elements of randomness and quantify the level of uncertainty in predictions. These methods use Bayes' theorem to evaluate results based on probability distributions. Examples of such methods include GPR and Relevance Vector Machine (RVM), which generate probabilistic predictions with confidence intervals.

On the other hand, deterministic methods do not involve probabilistic elements, and the results are based on known correlations between inputs and outputs, with precisely defined relationships between them. Deterministic models assume that the next state can be predicted with certainty based on the current state. Examples of such methods include various types of Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs), whose key sub-categories are FFNN and ANFIS, the latter of which integrates fuzzy logic. Deep Learning (DL) is another major category, defined as a multi-layered ANN, with prominent models such as Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN), Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN) and Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks. Other deterministic approaches include Support Vector Machines (SVM) and tree-based decision methods. [17,18,19]

ML methods are extensively employed across numerous research studies to estimate the degradation of Li-ion batteries [20,21,19,22]. In many cases, these methods are also used to estimate the State-of-Charge (SOC) of Li-ion batteries. For instance, Zheng et al. [8] applied SVM to estimate SOH, while using CNN with LSTM models to predict SOC, validating their approach with NASA battery datasets. The CNN-LSTM model is also applied in the research by Xu et al. [23], where it is used to estimate SOH.

SVM methods are also widely used for online SOH estimation in e-mobility applications, where they help indicate battery aging. In their study, Klass et al. [24] developed an SVM-based approach for estimating the SOH of Li-ion batteries in electric vehicles, achieving accurate estimations of capacity and resistance using onboard data. Similarly, Feng et al. [25] introduced an SVM-based SOH estimation technique that leverages partial charging segments, enabling rapid onboard diagnostics for Li-ion batteries.

ANNs are widely used for predicting the states of Li-ion batteries [26, 27,28,29,30,31] due to their adaptability to various data types and computational efficiency, making them also suitable for real-time applications. For example, in this research, Wu et al. [32] introduced an effective online method for estimating the Remaining Useful Life (RUL) of Li-ion batteries, combining a FFNN with importance sampling to enable accurate predictions of battery life during operation.

2.1. Support vector regression

SVR is an adaptation of SVM designed for regression tasks. SVR allows us to solve problems with small sample sizes and non-linear data. The function of this technique is the creation of hyperplanes in a high-dimensional space that provides a decision boundary for predicting

Fig. 1. Classification of ML methods into probabilistic and deterministic.

output values with high accuracy. To evaluate the SOH, the element data are transformed into a higher dimensional space and then linearly mapped and regressed to estimate the SOH values.

The sample set $S = \{(x_i, y_i), i = 1, 2, \dots, N\}$, where $x_i \in R^n$ and $y_i \in R$ represents the input and output feature vectors. Here, N is the total number of samples, and n refers to the dimensionality of the feature vectors. SVR utilizes a mapping function to transform the original low-dimensional data into a higher-dimensional feature space as defined by the equation:

$$f(x) = \omega \cdot \phi(x) + b \quad (2)$$

where ω is the weight vector, b is the bias, and $\phi(x)$ is the nonlinear mapping function. By introducing relaxation variables ζ and ζ^* , the objective of determining w and b can be formulated mathematically as below:

$$\min R(\omega, b, \bar{\zeta}) = \frac{1}{2} \|\omega\|^2 + C \sum_i^n (\bar{\zeta}_i + \bar{\zeta}_i^*) \quad (3)$$

The deviation between the predicted and actual values is confined within the margin of error ϵ for each data point, expressed as:

$$s.t. \begin{cases} y_i - \omega \cdot \phi(x) - b \leq \epsilon + \bar{\zeta}_i \\ \omega \cdot \phi(x) + b - y_i \leq \epsilon + \bar{\zeta}_i^* \\ \bar{\zeta}_i, \bar{\zeta}_i^* \geq 0. \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

In this context, C is a penalty parameter that regulates the balance between model complexity and the permissible error beyond ϵ . Through the introduction of Lagrange multipliers and the use of Kernel Functions (KFs), the SVR model can be reformulated as:

$$f(x) = \sum_{i=1}^N (\alpha_i - \alpha_i^*) K(x_i, x_j) + b \quad (5)$$

Here, (x_i, x_j) denotes the matrix of the KF, where x_i represents the input vectors for training, and x_j are the input vectors for the test samples. Lagrange multipliers are represented by α_i and α_i^* .

In SVR, several types of KFs can be applied, such as linear, polynomial, Gaussian or Radial Basis Function (RBF), and sigmoid kernels. The RBF kernel for every single vector is generally defined as:

$$\kappa_{\text{RBF}}(x, x') = \exp\left(-\frac{\|x - x'\|^2}{2l^2}\right) \quad (6)$$

where the parameter l is length scale, it determines how fast the similarity between two input points decreases with increasing distance between them. [33]

The SVR method can be further enhanced by combining it with other approaches to improve accuracy. This is exemplified by Li et al. [34], presenting a novel approach to estimate SOH in Li-ion batteries using an Improved Ant Lion Optimization algorithm (IALO) coupled with SVR.

2.2. Gaussian process regression

GPR is a probabilistic, non-parametric technique grounded in Bayes' theorem. Unlike other methods, such as SVR or neural networks, GPR directly captures model uncertainty and generates a confidence interval, indicating where the predicted values are likely located with a certain probability.

The Gaussian Process (GP) defines the probability distribution over a set of possible functions and is generally expressed as follows:

$$f(x) \sim GP(m(x), \kappa(x, x')) \quad (7)$$

where $m(x)$ represents the mean function and $\kappa(x, x')$ is the covariance function, also known as the KF.

$$m(x) = E[f(x)] \quad (8)$$

$$\kappa(x, x') = E[(f(x) - m(x))(f(x') - m(x'))^T] \quad (9)$$

Here, for a finite set of input points $X = x_1 \dots x_n$, the probability distribution is defined. In this case, it is Gaussian $p(f(x_1) \dots f(x_n))$ with mean $m(x)$ and covariance matrix $K(x)$, where $K_{ij} = \kappa(x_i, x_j)$.

The most commonly used covariance function is the Squared Exponential (SE), also known as RBF. In this experiment, the Rational Quadratic (RQ) KF is used. The parameter σ^2 is the output variance, which determines the range of prediction values.

$$k_{\text{RQ}}(x, x') = \sigma^2 \left(-\frac{\|x - x'\|^2}{2\alpha l^2} \right)^{-\alpha} \quad (10)$$

where the parameter α controls the relative weight between large and small-scale variations and l is the length scale.

GPR is a non-parametric regression method based on GP, where a general approach is used that does not require an exact definition of the function's form, such as linear or polynomial regression. The function $f(x)$ is considered a random sample from a GP, allowing the modeling of a set of possible functions without the need to define their shape in advance.

$$p(y^* | X^*, X, y) = \mathcal{N}(y^* | m^*, \text{cov}(y^*)) \quad (11)$$

This equation defines the prediction of new values y^* for new inputs X^* , with the result depending on the training data set (X, y) . The predicted mean m^* is computed from the covariance relations between the new points and the training points:

$$m^* = K(X^*, X)K(X, X)^{-1}y \quad (12)$$

The covariance of the prediction $\text{cov}(y^*)$ is computed from the covariance relations between the new points X^* and the training data X . [35,36]

$$\text{cov}(y^*) = K(X^*, X^*) - K(X^*, X)K(X, X)^{-1}K(X, X^*) \quad (13)$$

Numerous studies have demonstrated the effectiveness of the GPR method in achieving prominent results for battery state prediction. For example, Reddy et al. [37] applied GPR for SOH estimation in Li-ion batteries, utilizing indirect health indicators such as voltage, current, and temperature, and demonstrating high estimation accuracy. Similarly, Wang et al. [38] developed a modified GPR model for SOH estimation in Li-ion batteries, achieving a Mean Absolute Error (MAE) of 1.7 % and a Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) of 2.41 %.

2.3. Feed-Forward neural network

The ANN is designed to mathematically mimic the neural activity of the human brain and is one of the most popular algorithms for various applications, such as pattern recognition, optimization, and prediction. The FFNN consists of three main parts: input layer, Hidden Layers (HLs) and output layer. The input layer receives the data and forwards it directly to the HL. Each neuron in the HL then computes a weighted linear combination and, through an activation function, or more specifically, the Transfer Function (TF), forwards the information to the next HL. This process continues until the information reaches the output layer, which predicts the model's target output. The connections between these neurons can be represented by the i -th, j -th, and k -th nodes, respectively. During the forward pass in the output layer, the following computations occur:

$$\text{net}_k = \sum_{j=1}^n (w_{jk}y_j + b_k) \quad (14)$$

$$y_k = g(\text{net}_k) \quad (15)$$

where i represents the node in the input layer, j is a node in the HL, and k is a node in the output layer. Here, y is the output, b is the bias term, and

w_{ij} is the weight that connects nodes from one layer to another. The activation function is denoted as g , which can be a non-linear function that determines the output from the weighted sum of inputs. There are many types of activation functions, but the most popular ones are linear, sigmoid, hyperbolic tangent and Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU).

The backpropagation phase of the neural network involves adjusting the weights based on the gradient descent algorithm. The following rules guide the weight updates:

$$w_{ij}(t+1) = w_{ij}(t) + \Delta w_{ij} \quad (16)$$

$$\Delta w_{ij} = \eta(T_i - A_i)x_i \quad (17)$$

In these equations, η represents the learning rate, x_i is the input signal, T_i is the target output for a specific node, and A_i is the actual output. The weight change, Δw_{ij} , is applied to update the weights, improving the network's performance through this iterative process. [18,36,39]

2.4. Adaptive neuro-fuzzy inference systems

ANFIS integrate the principles of fuzzy logic with neural networks to construct models capable of learning from data to make predictions. Fuzzy logic transcends the rigid boundaries of classical Boolean logic by introducing the concept of partial membership, with truth values expressed on a continuum between 0 and 1. This enables the classification of variables into fuzzy sets with degrees of truth, rather than binary all-or-nothing classifications. In the neural network part of ANFIS, typically structured as a FFNN, input data is sequentially processed through the network layers to produce an output. The strength of ANFIS lies in its ability to approximate nonlinear functions. It accomplishes this by taking inputs and applying fuzzy logic to determine degrees of membership to various sets, a process known as fuzzification. This phase is followed by the application of fuzzy rules, based on T-norm operators which generalize the AND operation in fuzzy logic, to combine these memberships into a fuzzy result. These rules, derived from the Takagi-Sugeno model [40], guide the inference process in a forward pass through the system, which utilizes a least-squares method to optimize the rule parameters. This process is similar to the summation and activation functions commonly used in neural networks. The neural network then employs a form of gradient descent, such as backpropagation, to fine-tune the parameters of the fuzzy system, including the shape of the Membership Functions (MFs) and the weights in the fuzzy rules, based on training data. The final step, defuzzification, converts the fuzzy classification into a crisp output, which represents the model's

prediction. [41,42]

The ANFIS architecture incorporates a set of fuzzy if-then rules of a Sugeno model, each with its own set of input-output pairs. In general, the following two rules are defined for a typical first-order Sugeno fuzzy model [42]:

Rule 1: If x_1 is A_1 and x_2 is B_1 , then $f_1 = p_1 x_1 + q_1 x_2 + r_1$

Rule 2: If x_1 is A_2 and x_2 is B_2 , then $f_2 = p_2 x_1 + q_2 x_2 + r_2$

where x_1 and x_2 are the input variables, and A_i, B_i represent the fuzzy sets associated with these inputs. The output functions f_1 and f_2 are linear combinations of the input variables and their respective rule-specific parameters p_i, q_i , and r_i .

The ANFIS structure is generally divided into five layers: fuzzification layer, rule layer, normalization layer, defuzzification layer, and output layer (see Fig. 2). In the Fuzzification layer, each node is adaptive. This layer directly interacts with the input variables x_1 and x_2 in this case. The nodes here act as fuzzifiers, converting crisp input values into degrees of membership using fuzzy sets. The parameters of these fuzzy sets are modifiable, which allows the system to learn from data. For instance, the bell-shaped MF is commonly used, which is defined by three parameters a_i, b_i and c_i . These parameters determine the width, slope, and center of the bell curve, accordingly. It outputs the membership grade of an input variable for a given fuzzy set A_i or $B_i - 2$.

$$O_{1,i} = \mu_{A_i}(x_1), \quad i = 1, 2 \quad \text{or} \quad O_{1,i} = \mu_{B_{i-2}}(x_2), \quad i = 3, 4 \quad (18)$$

Where $\mu_{A_i}(x_1), \mu_{B_{i-2}}(x_2)$ are membership functions for fuzzy sets $A_i, B_i - 2$. The bell-shaped MF may be represented by the following equation:

$$\mu_A(x_1) = \frac{1}{1 + \left| \frac{x_1 - c_i}{a_i} \right|^{2b}} \quad (19)$$

The Rule layer comprises a set of fixed nodes, each representing a fuzzy rule. The output of each node is the product of all the incoming signals, which corresponds to the application of a fuzzy operator (AND in the case of Sugeno models) to the membership grades from Layer 1. The output is the firing strength of a rule w_i , which indicates the degree to which the antecedent part of the fuzzy rule is satisfied.

$$O_{2,i} = w_i = \mu_{A_i}(x_1)\mu_{B_i}(x_2), \quad i = 1, 2 \quad (20)$$

In the Normalization layer, the rule strengths are normalized. The nodes in this layer are fixed and calculate the ratio of each rule's firing strength to the sum of all rules' firing strengths. This normalization process ensures that the sum of the normalized firing strengths is equal

Fig. 2. A five-layer ANFIS structure consisting of fuzzification, rule layer, normalization, defuzzification, and output.

to one, which prepares the system for the defuzzification process in the subsequent layers.

$$O_{3,i} = \bar{w}_i = \frac{w_i}{w_1 + w_2}, \quad i = 1, 2 \quad (21)$$

where \bar{w}_i is the normalized firing strength.

Defuzzification layer contains adaptive nodes that calculate the contribution of each rule to the final output. Each node's output is a function of the input variables, modulated by the normalized firing strength from Layer 3 and the consequent parameters of the rule. These parameters are analogous to the coefficients in a linear regression model and are tuned during the training process to map the fuzzy rules to the desired output.

$$O_{4,i} = \bar{w}_i f_i = \bar{w}_i (p_i x_1 + q_i x_2 + r_i), \quad (22)$$

The last one represents output layer, which aggregates the contributions from all the rules to produce a single crisp output. The single node in this layer sums the weighted outputs provided by Layer 4, which is the defuzzified value. The weights here are the normalized firing strengths from Layer 3, ensuring that rules with higher applicability have a more significant impact on the final output.

$$O_{5,i} = \sum_i \bar{w}_i f_i = \frac{\sum_i w_i f_i}{\sum_i w_i} \quad (23)$$

By adjusting the parameters in Layers 1 and 4 through learning, ANFIS can approximate nonlinear functions. This learning is typically done through methods borrowed from neural network training, such as backpropagation and least squares estimation, enabling the system to refine its parameters to better model complex relationships between inputs and outputs.

ANFIS is an adaptable method, though it can be sensitive to data with high noise levels or weak correlations, which may affect SOH estimation accuracy. In some cases, selecting optimized data or incorporating noise-suppression techniques can further improve ANFIS's predictive performance. For example, Meng et al. [43] developed a hybrid approach combining complete ensemble empirical mode decomposition with adaptive noise and ANFIS to enhance the accuracy of Li-ion battery capacity predictions by addressing regeneration effects. Validation on NASA Li-ion battery data demonstrated that this approach effectively reduces the negative impact of capacity regeneration, improving prediction accuracy.

2.5. Fine-tuning

Fine-tuning is a transfer learning technique that enables a pre-trained ML model to adapt to a new dataset with minimal additional training data, improving generalization without requiring the model to be trained from scratch. This process refines the model's parameters using a smaller, task-specific dataset, optimizing its predictions for a new but related problem. Fine-tuning is particularly effective in applications where data collection is costly or limited, as it leverages prior knowledge while improving performance in a new domain.

In this study, fine-tuning is applied to enhance the adaptability of SOH estimation models across different battery datasets. Specifically, a model trained on one Li-ion battery dataset is fine-tuned using a subset of another battery's data, allowing it to learn battery-specific degradation characteristics while retaining general predictive capability. This approach ensures improved accuracy and robustness when transitioning between different battery chemistries or operational conditions.

The effectiveness of fine-tuning for battery health estimation has been demonstrated in previous studies. Che et al. in [44] applied fine-tuning in conjunction with transfer learning and online model correction, enabling models to adapt dynamically to new degradation patterns and achieve high-accuracy RUL predictions. Similarly, Che et al. in [45] introduced a self-learning framework that fine-tunes

battery lifetime prediction models using a limited number of labeled data points and self-generated pseudo-labels, reducing reliance on extensive training datasets.

3. Experimental

The research was conducted on Samsung INR18650–35E batteries, which have a nominal capacity of 3.4 Ah with lithium-nickel-manganese-cobalt oxides (NMC) as the cathode material and graphite as the anode material. Testing was performed at room temperature using the Constant Current Constant Voltage (CCCV) charging method and Constant Current (CC) discharging, with a total of 600 cycles. The batteries were charged at a constant current of 0.5 C until reaching a voltage of 4.2 V, after which the constant voltage phase was initiated until the current reaches 68 mA. The discharge cut-off voltage was set at 2.65 V. Further specifications of the Samsung INR18650–35E batteries are outlined in Table 1.

Fig. 3 shows the trend of the SOH of two batteries at ambient temperature, ranging from a new battery state to an SOH of approximately 0.82.

Additional tests were performed on the battery at 100-cycle intervals, during which batteries were temporarily removed from operation. This process resulted in an increase in the capacity of the battery throughout the cycling procedure.

3.1. Feature extraction

In this study, features are manually extracted from measured values, which requires domain knowledge and additional analysis. Nevertheless, this method can reduce prediction error. There are also studies where features are extracted automatically; for instance, Jiang et al. [46] proposed an automated approach employing a convolutional

Table 1
Parameters of Samsung INR18650–35E battery.

Parameter	Value
Type	Cylindric
Nominal Capacity	3.4 Ah
Nominal Voltage	3.6 V
Maximum Voltage	4.2 V
Minimum Voltage	2.65 V
Max. Continuous Discharge Current	8 A

Fig. 3. SOH of two Samsung INR18650–35E batteries, labeled as Battery 1 (B1) and Battery 2 (B2).

autoencoder for feature extraction and a self-attention mechanism to enhance prediction accuracy.

In this case, seven features were selected for SOH estimation, extracted from the measured data and analyzed for correlation. While the experiment primarily focuses on features from charging cycles, it also incorporates parameters from discharging cycles to improve estimation accuracy. This combination enables a more comprehensive analysis, as discharging characteristics contribute valuable insights into the battery's overall behavior.

Although the study is based on controlled laboratory measurements, it reflects real-world scenarios where batteries are often discharged randomly, while the charging process remains consistent through the CCCV method once a certain discharge voltage is reached. By using parameters from both charging and discharging cycles, the experiment provides a more comprehensive approach to SOH estimation, enhancing its practical applicability.

The first indicator of capacity decline that can be used for SOH prediction is the time when the voltage reaches a specific milestone during the CC phase. From Fig. 4 (a), it is evident that as the number of cycles increases, the time to reach 4.2 V decreases, specifically at the point where charging switches into the CV phase. In this case, the voltage ranges from 3.2 V to 4.15 V, denoted as $t_{V(ch)}$, was selected.

Shu et al. [47] analyzed the correlations of this parameter depending on the selected voltage range, finding that for the range of 3.4 V to 4.1 V, the correlation approached 1 for the studied sample. Fig. 4 (b) shows a strong similarity to the SOH of B1 across the entire range, which could be attributed to the choice of a wide charging voltage range. Based on visual analysis, this parameter suggests that $t_{V(ch)}$ could be defined as a good feature for SOH estimation.

The next feature is derived from the discharge cycles, where the time from the start of discharging a fully charged battery until the voltage drops to 3.6 V is monitored, and it is labelled as $t_{V(d)}$ (see Fig. 5 (a)). Although this input is affected by noise, it exhibits a strong correlation or similarity from approximately 50 cycles onwards (see Fig. 5 (b)). In this case, it is possible to estimate SOH in a significantly shorter time compared to other parameters, with high accuracy.

The third input for prediction was extracted from current profiles during the charging phase. Significant changes occur primarily during the CV phase, where the discharge curve shifts as the number of battery cycles increases. In Fig. 6 (a), the individual current drop profiles at the 1st and every 100th cycle, up to 500 cycles, are shown, and it is evident that the current drops earlier. The threshold of 0.5 A was chosen on the assumption that the battery would not reach full charge. The time interval between the start of charging and when the current reaches 0.5 A

(a) Voltage profile during the charging cycles of B1.

(b) Extracted time interval between 3.2 V and 4.2 V for each cycle of B1.

Fig. 4. Extracted time-dependent feature $t_{V(ch)}$ (b) from charging voltage curves (a).

(a) Voltage profile during the discharging cycles of B1.

(b) Extracted time interval between start of discharging and 3.6 V for each cycle of B1.

Fig. 5. Extracted time-dependent feature $t_{V(d)}$ (b) from discharging voltage curves (a).

(a) Current profile during the charging cycles of B1.

(b) Time interval of the current drop to 0.5 A during the CV phase for B1.

Fig. 6. Extracted time dependent feature $t_I(ch)$ (b) from current drop during CV phase (a).

is defined as $t_I(ch)$, and its dependence on the number of cycles is illustrated in Fig. 6 (b).

The battery was measured at ambient temperature; however, even the ambient temperature exhibited significant fluctuations in this case. The average temperature T_{avg} of the battery cell, shown as a function of cycles in Fig. 7, is also used as an indicator for SOH estimation, as temperature can play a key role in the battery's degradation mechanisms.

The predictor $t_{Tpeak(ch)}$ represents the time to reach the maximum temperature during the charging cycle (see Fig. 8 (a)). This peak occurs during the transition from the CC phase to the CV phase. Although this feature is highlighted in this research [48] as having a high correlation, that is not the case here. The ambient temperature is affected by significant fluctuations and variations during the measurements, which degrades the quality of this input. As shown in Fig. 8 (b), while the input maintains a certain SOH trend, it also contains substantial noise, which can negatively impact the results.

The battery was charged using the CCCV method, and from previous findings, it is clear that as the number of cycles performed on the battery increases, the charging time also shortens, particularly during the CC phase, where the battery is charged at 0.5 C or a current of 1.7 A. As a result, the battery reaches 4.2 V more quickly during the charging

Fig. 7. Average operational temperature T_{avg} of the battery cell.

process, leading to a gradual increase in the average voltage during charging cycles (see Fig. 9). This feature, denoted as $V_{avg(ch)}$, represents the average voltage measured during charging cycles, including both the CC and potentiostatic phases. It is evident that $V_{avg(ch)}$ has a strong negative correlation with SOH.

During the discharge cycles, the duration until the battery reaches the cut-off voltage of 2.65 V decreases. The average discharge voltage $V_{avg(d)}$ also slightly declines with the number of cycles (see Fig. 10), providing additional insights into battery aging.

3.2. Feature selection

Although all the parameters visually suggest certain correlations with the battery's SOH, they were subjected to mutual correlation analysis to determine the strength of their correlation with SOH and how they correlate with each other. Specifically, Pearson correlation analysis was used in this experiment. The value of the correlation coefficient is represented by $\rho_{X,Y}$.

$$\rho_{X,Y} = \frac{\text{cov}(X, Y)}{\sigma_X \sigma_Y} = \frac{\sum XY - \frac{1}{N} \sum X \sum Y}{\sqrt{\left(\sum X^2 - \frac{1}{N}(\sum X)^2\right) \left(\sum Y^2 - \frac{1}{N}(\sum Y)^2\right)}} \quad (24)$$

Here X and Y represent two random variables, where $\text{cov}(X, Y)$ denotes their covariance, σ_X and σ_Y is the standard deviation and N is the length of the dataset. In Fig. 11 and Fig. 12, the mutual correlations between the individual inputs and SOH are depicted, highlighting that $t_V(ch)$, $t_V(d)$, $t_I(ch)$, $V_{avg(ch)}$ and $V_{avg(d)}$ will significantly contribute to the estimation of SOH. The temperature has a weaker correlation, but it can still provide valuable insights for predicting battery degradation. In contrast, the correlation between the peak temperature $t_{Tpeak(ch)}$ and SOH is weak, and the significant noise in the data may reduce the accuracy of the prediction.

3.3. Root mean square error

The comparison of the overall error for each method is performed using the RMSE, which is calculated as the square root of the average squared differences between the actual and estimated values obtained through ML. Mathematically, RMSE is expressed as:

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2} \quad (25)$$

(a) The temperature during the charging cycles of B1

(b) Extracted temperature peak during the charging cycles of B1.

Fig. 8. Time to reach the temperature peak during charging cycles $t_{Tpeak (ch)}$.

Fig. 9. Average charging voltage $V_{avg (ch)}$ of the battery cell.

Fig. 10. Average discharging voltage $V_{avg (d)}$ of the battery cell.

Where n is cycle number, y_i represents measured data and \hat{y}_i is the estimated SOH value.

3.4. Exhaustive search

Due to the high sensitivity of the ANFIS method to overfitting, relying solely on a correlation matrix to determine appropriate inputs for SOH estimation is insufficient. Thus, a more comprehensive analysis utilizing the Exhaustive Search (ES) method is required. This method evaluates input combinations by calculating the RMSE of the estimated output for both training and testing datasets, using a single epoch for evaluation. Typically, simple configurations are applied, such as a minimal number of epochs and MFs, allowing for a quick and efficient analysis. Despite this, RMSE values for certain input combinations can vary as the number of epochs increases. To solve this, a matrix was constructed to analyze RMSE across various epoch counts (ranging from 1 to 30) and different combinations of 2 to 4 inputs, using a training dataset of 290 cycles, corresponding to half of the full dataset.

It is important to note that selecting the combination with the lowest error was not always optimal, as certain combinations exhibited a low error at 290 cycles but significantly higher errors with smaller or larger datasets. This issue is explored further in Fig. 13, Fig. 14, Fig. 15 for B1 and Fig. 16, Fig. 17, Fig. 18 for B2.

For B1, various input combinations were analyzed, with the combination of three inputs: $t_{V (ch)}$, $t_{V (d)}$, and $t_{I (ch)}$ being selected as it showed the lowest test RMSE with $\frac{1}{2}$ of the test dataset and 10 epochs. On the other hand, combinations of three inputs can exhibit significantly higher RMSE than other types of combinations, even those involving inputs with very strong correlations.

For B2, the combination of two inputs, $t_{I (ch)}$ and $V_{avg (ch)}$, was selected at 11 epochs. This combination exhibits a higher test RMSE but has lower volatility when the length of the training dataset changes. This characteristic can only be identified based on feedback from the results.

Due to the fact that ANFIS is a method highly sensitive to overfitting, it is also necessary to observe its behavior with different training dataset lengths. New information in a bigger dataset can significantly affect the SOH estimation behavior when using ANFIS, and as a result, using $\frac{1}{2}$ of the training data may sometimes result in a higher RMSE than using $\frac{1}{3}$ of the training data.

Fig. 11. Pearson correlation analysis between features and output of B1.

Fig. 12. Pearson correlation analysis between features and output of B2.

4. Results and discussion

The research was conducted over 600 cycles of a Li-ion batteries using the CCCV method, although only 580 cycles were used due to measurement inaccuracies. Four ML methods were employed for the estimation analysis: SVR, GPR, FFNN and ANFIS. Each method was analyzed with different amounts of data, each demonstrated slightly different estimation errors. The techniques are also subject to various additional tests, including overfitting analysis, tracking the RMSE of each method from 190 to 400 cycles in every cycle, and the final test of SOH estimation for B2 based on training data from B1.

4.1. SOH estimation with 1/3, 1/2, and 2/3 of the training dataset

Each method was tested with different lengths of the training dataset: 194 cycles (1/3 of the data), 290 cycles (1/2 of the data), and 387

cycles (2/3 of the data). This test was conducted to evaluate each method under varying conditions with the selected optimal combination of features. The SVR, GPR and FFNN methods use different input types compared to the ANFIS method due to its volatility, which is analyzed in other cases.

For B1, only a combination of two inputs, t_V (ch) and t_I (ch), was used for the first three ML methods. The ANFIS method, on the other hand, is based on the ES analysis to define the most compatible inputs across different training data lengths and uses a combination of three inputs: t_V (ch), t_V (d), and t_I (ch), with 21 epochs and 2 MFs. The remaining configured parameters for each method are presented in Table 2.

Fig. 19 compares the results of the individual ML methods both visually (a, c, e) and by displaying the absolute error at each point of SOH estimation (b, d, g). The highest absolute error, nearly 0.02, occurs with the ANFIS method using 1/3 of the training data in the final predicted cycles. In other cases, the maximum error is more significant with

Fig. 13. ES for the combination of two features from B1, using 5 epochs and 290 training data cycles.

Fig. 14. ES for the combination of three features from B1, using 20 epochs and 290 training data cycles.

the FFNN technique. In this case, it can be concluded that SVR, with its simplicity, maintains highly prominent results. The GPR method is generally more accurate when using larger datasets, though even with 2/3 of the training data, the ANFIS method prevails, achieving an RMSE of 0.13 %. It should be noted that the performance of ANFIS depends on the selected inputs, as it exhibits high volatility. The remaining RMSE results are compared in Table 3, Table 4

To ensure reproducibility, an experiment was also conducted for B2, though it was not possible to use the same configuration for the ANFIS

method. Due to its sensitivity to variations in the dataset and the slightly different trend observed in B2, an additional ES analysis was necessary, and in this case, the inputs $t_V(ch)$ and $V_{avg}(ch)$ were more compatible.

For B2, the results improved, particularly for SVR and FFNN, especially with 2/3 of the training dataset, in all cases except for ANFIS. The results for ANFIS remained the same or became worse. Nevertheless, even in this case, the RMSE stayed below 0.5. All results are compared again in Fig. 20, with the overall RMSE presented in Table 5.

Fig. 15. ES for the combination of four features from B1, using 10 epochs and 290 training data cycles.

Fig. 16. ES for the combination of two features from B2, using 11 epochs and 290 training data cycles.

4.2. Evaluation of ml methods for soh estimation under overfitting conditions

In the next experiment, the individual methods were subjected to overfitting analysis for B1, using all features that visually correspond with the SOH trend and have a correlation with SOH greater than 0.7 in the correlation matrix. Although T_{avg} does not show a strong correlation with SOH, it can still provide valuable information about battery degradation. On the other hand, $t_{Ipeak}(ch)$ is unfortunately affected by significant noise, which would only degrade the estimation results. For

SOH estimation, half of the training data was used, with the following inputs: $t_V(ch)$, $t_V(d)$, $t_I(ch)$, T_{avg} , $V_{avg}(ch)$ and $V_{avg}(d)$.

As seen in Fig. 21, the ANFIS method shows strong signs of overfitting compared to the other methods. GVR and FFNN also display weaker results, likely due to an incorrectly defined SOH trend vector, which may have been influenced by one of the inputs. The best results are produced by the simplest method, SVR, which, according to Table 6, has a total RMSE of 0.5 % and demonstrates strong resistance to overfitting. Despite this, the RMSE for all methods remains exceptionally low.

Fig. 17. ES for the combination of three features from B2, using 10 epochs and 290 training data cycles. (2nd choice).

Fig. 18. ES for the combination of four features from B2, using 10 epochs and 290 training data cycles.

Table 2
Configuration of ML techniques and input features for SOH estimation of B1.

Method	Settings	Inputs
SVR	KF = gaussian	$t_{V(ch)}$, $t_{I(ch)}$
GPR	KF = rationalquadratic, Basis f. = pureQuadratic	$t_{V(ch)}$, $t_{I(ch)}$
FFNN	TF = purelin, HL = 3, neurons = 5/HL	$t_{V(ch)}$, $t_{I(ch)}$
ANFIS	MFs = 2, MF type = gaussmf, Epoch num. = 21	$t_{V(ch)}$, $t_{V(d)}$, $t_{I(ch)}$

4.3. Comparison of ml methods based on continuous dataset length

The individual methods were also compared based on the length of the dataset used, ranging from 190 to 400 cycles. These tests allow for defining the actual variability of the ANFIS method. The inputs were the same as in the first test, where the ANFIS technique showed relatively prominent results, especially in the later phases as mentioned earlier,

due to the choice of inputs, this method can show varying RMSE at different cycles. From 1/3 of the dataset onward, the RMSE for the ANFIS technique rises to over 16 % (see Fig. 22).

The inputs were selected based on the defined training data, where they demonstrated the lowest error compared to other input combinations. Therefore, at this stage, they may be more effective. If the goal is to make predictions based on the number of cycles, it is advisable to choose a configuration that may result in a higher RMSE at specific observed points but provides more stable results within the defined training data window. Fig. 23 presents several possible combinations for ANFIS, ranging from 2 to 4 inputs, depending on the amount of training data.

The parameters chosen for the ANFIS analysis are based on the ES results for B1 with a combination of 2 inputs, where $t_{V(ch)}$, $t_{V(d)}$, $V_{avg(ch)}$, and $V_{avg(d)}$ performed the best in various combinations. In the first case, the selected combination is the one used in the initial test for

Fig. 19. SOH estimation for B1 using 1/3, 1/2, and 2/3 of the dataset as the training set, along with the corresponding absolute estimation error.

Table 3
Comparison of RMSE for SVR, GPR, FFNN, and ANFIS methods with different amounts of training data for B1.

	Training cycles [-]	Method			
		SVR	GPR	FFNN	ANFIS
RMSE [%]	194 (1/3)	0.30	0.29	0.24	0.47
	290 (1/2)	0.18	0.19	0.37	0.20
	387 (2/3)	0.20	0.18	0.29	0.13

Table 4
Configuration of ML techniques and input features for SOH estimation of B1.

Method	Settings	Inputs
SVR	KF = gaussian	$t_V(ch)$, $t_I(ch)$
GPR	KF = rationalquadratic, Basis f. = pureQuadratic	$t_V(ch)$, $t_I(ch)$
FFNN	TF = purelin, HL = 3, neurons = 5/HL	$t_V(ch)$, $t_I(ch)$
ANFIS	MFs = 2, MF type = gaussmf, Epoch num. = 11	$t_V(ch)$, $V_{avg}(ch)$

demonstrating the estimation error at 1/3, 1/2, and 2/3 of the training dataset. The second case identifies the most stable combination for B1,

Fig. 20. SOH estimation for B2 using 1/3, 1/2, and 2/3 of the dataset as the training set, along with the corresponding absolute estimation error.

Table 5
Comparison of RMSE for SVR, GPR, FFNN, and ANFIS methods with different amounts of training data for B2.

	Training cycles [-]	Method			
		SVR	GPR	FFNN	ANFIS
RMSE [%]	194 (1/3)	0.21	0.43	0.21	0.48
	290 (1/2)	0.14	0.35	0.15	0.4
	387 (2/3)	0.14	0.15	0.15	0.15

while the next combination is the same but includes temperature to examine its influence on the SOH estimation results. The 4-input combination is considered the best possible for B1 and is directly derived from the ES results. For B2, although other combinations might be more suitable, the same ones were selected for direct comparison. The combinations used for B1 and B2 are defined in Table 7.

In the case of B2, none of the methods exceed 3 % RMSE, with SVR and FFNN remaining below the 0.5 RMSE threshold throughout. The ANFIS method again achieves the lowest RMSE at the defined points of the first test, but it fluctuates across the entire continuum, though not as significantly as in B1 (see Fig. 24).

(a) SOH estimation for B1 (TD = 290 cycles).

(b) Error in SOH estimation for B1 (TD = 290 cycles).

Fig. 21. SOH estimation for B1 using half of the dataset and multiple features to detect overfitting.

Table 6

Comparison of RMSE for SVR, GPR, FFNN, and ANFIS techniques under overfitting conditions for B1.

		Method			
	Training cycles [-]	SVR	GPR	FFNN	ANFIS
RMSE [%]	290 (1/2)	0.19	0.56	0.48	0.81

Fig. 22. RMSE of SVR, GPR, FFNN, and ANFIS methods based on the number of training cycles from 190 to 400 for B1.

In the comparison of the best possible combinations for the ANFIS method, overfitting was observed in the fourth combination, which yielded the worst results (see Fig. 25). Although the combination of $t_I(ch)$ and $V_{avg}(d)$ may seem the most promising, its RMSE increases significantly as the number of cycles grows.

4.4. SOH estimation for B1 and B2 using cross-dataset training

The final experiment involves the estimation of SOH for B2 using training data from B1. This approach is feasible under the assumption that the batteries are identical and were tested under the same conditions. In other words, the SOH responses to the inputs should be similar,

Fig. 23. RMSE of ANFIS technique based on the number of training cycles from 190 to 400 for B1.

Table 7

Specification of input features used in ANFIS for both batteries.

Case	Combination of input features
1.	The same combination as in the first test.
2.	$t_I(ch), V_{avg}(d)$
3.	$t_I(ch), V_{avg}(d), T_{avg}$
4.	$t_V(ch), t_V(d), V_{avg}(ch), V_{avg}(d)$

enabling the estimation of SOH for B2 based on input values obtained from its measurements. This is feasible because the relationships between inputs and outputs for B1 were clearly established during the training process. In this experiment, more inputs were required compared to previous cases: $t_V(ch)$, $t_V(d)$, $t_I(ch)$, and $V_{avg}(ch)$. The configuration of the ML methods is described in Table 8.

Fig. 26 (a) illustrates both the SOH of B1 and B2, along with the estimated SOH using various methods. In the initial phase, up to approximately 290 cycles, the trend closely follows the SOH of B2. From the midpoint onward, it tends to align more with the SOH of B1. This is also evident in Fig. 26 (b), where the absolute error of the prediction increases. Table 9 compares the overall RMSE of the individual methods,

Fig. 24. RMSE of SVR, GPR, FFNN, and ANFIS methods based on the number of training cycles from 190 to 400 for B2.

Fig. 25. RMSE of ANFIS technique based on the number of training cycles from 190 to 400 for B2.

Table 8
Configuration of ML techniques and input features for SOH estimation of B1.

Method	Settings	Inputs
SVR	KF = gaussian	$t_{V(ch)}$, $t_{V(d)}$, $V_{avg(ch)}$, $V_{avg(d)}$
GPR	KF = rationalquadratic, Basis f. = pureQuadratic	$t_{V(ch)}$, $t_{V(d)}$, $V_{avg(ch)}$, $V_{avg(d)}$
FFNN	TF = purelin, HL = 3, neurons = 5/HL	
ANFIS	MFs = 2, MF type = gaussmf, Epoch num. = 125	

where all methods show nearly identical results.

To achieve better results, fine-tuning was applied, incorporating not only the training data from B1 but also the first 50 cycles from B2 for a more accurate identification of dependencies between the individual pairs, leading to an improved estimation. Additionally, only 350 cycles from B1 were used to reduce the inclination toward the original SOH of B1, as using the entire dataset negatively impacted the estimation of SOH for B2 due to its trend.

Fig. 27 clearly shows that, in this case, the overall estimation is much more accurate, and the maximum absolute error has decreased. Although a certain deviation occurs approximately every 100 cycles,

particularly with the ANFIS and FFNN methods, the FFNN method achieved the best results in terms of overall RMSE (see Table 10).

In addition to the prediction of B2, the reverse experiment was also conducted for B1 to evaluate the performance of individual models. In this case, a more sophisticated configuration was required for selected methods. For GPR, it was necessary to adjust the KF and test auto-optimization of the remaining parameters. For FFNN, a more complex network architecture was implemented, incorporating a log-sigmoid TF and a linear output layer. In addition to modifying the network's TF, the number of neurons was increased, and Bayesian regularization was applied. These modifications enabled an RMSE below 0.5% to be achieved.

The selected input features were $t_{V(ch)}$, $t_{I(ch)}$ and $V_{avg(ch)}$. The parameters $t_{V(d)}$ and $V_{avg(ch)}$ introduced significant error, particularly in fine-tuning, compared to the previous case. Conversely, $t_{I(ch)}$ was included, as it exhibited high correlation during feature selection. Further details on the experimental setup are provided in Table 11.

The results shown in Fig. 28 do not differ in performance from the previous model, as confirmed by the RMSE comparison of individual models in Table 12. The model exhibits lower RMSE up to cycle 290, while in later phases, it tends to align more closely with the training SOH, specifically SOH_{B2}.

When the model was fine-tuned with 50 cycles from battery B1, the error was reduced by approximately one-third, while the results of the individual models remained nearly identical. However, it should be noted that FFNN has a more complex configuration compared to the previous case, and achieving this level of accuracy would not have been possible with the original, simpler setup. The results are presented in Fig. 29 and compared in Table 13.

4.5. Validation test on a prismatic cell

To further evaluate the generalization capabilities of ML models in SOH estimation, a publicly available dataset of prismatic Li-ion batteries, created by Klvač et al. [49], was incorporated into the analysis. This dataset, from the work published by Stravova et al. [50], titled "Comprehensive study of rapid capacity fade in prismatic Li-ion cells with flexible packaging", examines degradation mechanisms and structural failures in prismatic Li-ion batteries using X-ray computed tomography and scanning electron microscopy.

The dataset comprises 100 electrochemical cycles, utilizing CCCV charging and CC discharging techniques. During this period, the cell experienced a rapid capacity fade of approximately 40%. The battery parameters are detailed in Table 14.

The model configurations were adjusted to enhance estimation accuracy. SVR was implemented with a linear KF, while GPR utilized an auto-optimization method. For FFNN, a purelin TF was applied with three hidden layers. The selected input features were $t_{V(ch)}$ and $t_{I(ch)}$. Further details on the simulation setup are provided in Table 15.

The test was conducted using only half of the dataset for training. The results for the prismatic battery were quite worse than in previous cases, primarily due to the rapid capacity fade, which was less pronounced in the training data. The GPR model performed the worst in this test, as it could not be sufficiently optimized. This error may not have been caused solely by the different initial degradation trend but also by the limited number of cycles available for training, as the battery had already experienced significant degradation after just 100 cycles. The estimation trend is shown in Fig. 30, and a more detailed RMSE comparison of individual models is provided in Table 16.

4.6. Summary

The comparison in Table 17 highlights the strengths and limitations of SVR, GPR, FFNN, and ANFIS across different dataset conditions, fine-tuning, and cross-validation scenarios. Each method demonstrates distinct characteristics depending on dataset size, feature correlations,

(a) SOH estimation for B2 (TD 580 cycles from B1).

(b) Error in SOH estimation for B2 (TD 580 cycles from B1).

Fig. 26. SOH estimation for B2 using the entire training dataset from B1.

Table 9

Comparison of RMSE for SVR, GPR, FFNN, and ANFIS techniques for SOH estimation of B2 using the training dataset from B1.

RMSE [%]	Training cycles [-]	Method			
		SVR	GPR	FFNN	ANFIS
	580 (B1)	0.59	0.60	0.61	0.62

and sensitivity to overfitting.

SVR is a robust and stable method, demonstrating consistent performance across different dataset sizes and exhibiting strong resistance to overfitting. However, its ability to capture complex nonlinear relationships is limited, which may result in lower performance when highly correlated features are available or in cases where larger datasets enable more expressive models to achieve lower RMSE.

GPR is highly effective when trained on larger datasets, as it can accurately model complex dependencies within the data. Anyway, it is susceptible to overfitting, particularly when applied to smaller datasets or less informative features, as observed in the Prismatic cell test. This sensitivity can lead to a degradation in predictive performance when generalizing to different datasets.

FFNN provides stable and adaptable predictions, particularly excelling in fine-tuning and cross-validation, as demonstrated in the B2 on B1 fine-tuning test. Due to the availability of various optimization

Table 10

Comparison of RMSE for SVR, GPR, FFNN, and ANFIS techniques for SOH estimation of B2 using the training dataset from B1 with fine-tuning from B2.

RMSE [%]	Training cycles [-]	Method			
		SVR	GPR	FFNN	ANFIS
	350 (B1), 50 (B2)	0.45	0.45	0.39	0.51

Table 11

Configuration of ML techniques and input features for SOH estimation of B1.

Method	Settings	Inputs
SVR	KF = gaussian	$t_V^{(ch)}$, $t_I^{(ch)}$
GPR	KF = squaredexponential, Auto optimization	$V_{avg}^{(ch)}$
FFNN	TF = logsig/purelin, HL = 3, neurons = 10/HL, Bayesian regularization	
ANFIS	MFs = 2, MF type = gaussmf, Epoch num. = 8	

(a) SOH est. for B2 (TD 350 cycles from B1, FT 50 cycles from B2).

(b) Error in SOH est. for B2 (TD 350 cycles from B1, FT 50 cycles from B2).

Fig. 27. SOH estimation for B2 using the training dataset from B1 with fine-tuning.

(a) SOH estimation for B1 (TD 580 cycles from B2).

(b) Error in SOH estimation for B1 (TD 580 cycles from B2).

Fig. 28. SOH estimation for B1 using the training dataset from B2.

Table 12

Comparison of RMSE for SVR, GPR, FFNN, and ANFIS techniques for SOH estimation of B1 using the training dataset from B2.

RMSE [%]	Training cycles [-]	Method			
		SVR	GPR	FFNN	ANFIS
	580 (B1)	0.59	0.60	0.60	0.60

techniques, the model can be adjusted more effectively than other approaches. But its performance is occasionally dependent on proper architecture tuning, and without appropriate regularization and hyperparameter optimization, it may underperform relative to simpler models.

ANFIS, when optimized with well-correlated features and sufficiently large datasets, achieves high predictive accuracy. Its ability to capture complex relationships makes it well-suited for structured data. However, it is prone to overfitting, particularly when features with lower correlation to SOH are present.

Table 13

Comparison of RMSE for SVR, GPR, FFNN, and ANFIS techniques for SOH estimation of B1 using the training dataset from B2 with fine-tuning from B1.

RMSE [%]	Training cycles [-]	Method			
		SVR	GPR	FFNN	ANFIS
	350 (B2), 50 (B1)	0.40	0.43	0.42	0.42

Table 14

Parameters of prismatic cell.

Parameter	Value
Type	Prismatic
Nominal Capacity	150 mAh
Nominal Voltage	3.7 V
Maximum Voltage	4.2 V
Minimum Voltage	2.75 V
Max. Continuous Discharge Current	1 A

(a) SOH est. for B1 (TD 350 cycles from B2, FT 50 cycles from B1).

(b) Error in SOH est. for B1 (TD 350 cycles from B2, FT 50 cycles from B1).

Fig. 29. SOH estimation for B1 using the training dataset from B2 with fine-tuning.

Table 15
Configuration of ML techniques and input features for SOH estimation of prismatic cell.

Method	Settings	Inputs
SVR	KF = linear	$t_{V(ch)}$, $t_I(ch)$
GPR	KF = ardrationalquadratic, Basis f. = linear	
FFNN	TF = purelin, HL = 3, neurons = [2 20 2]	
ANFIS	MFs = 2, MF type = gaussmf, Epoch num. = 4	

(a) SOH estimation for prismatic cell (TD = 50 cycles).

(b) Error in SOH estimation for prismatic cell (TD = 50 cycles).

Fig. 30. SOH estimation for prismatic cell using 1/2 of the dataset as the training set, along with the corresponding absolute estimation error.

Table 16
Comparison of RMSE for SVR, GPR, FFNN, and ANFIS methods with different amounts of training data for prismatic cell.

RMSE [%]	Training cycles [-]	Method			
		SVR	GPR	FFNN	ANFIS
	290 (1/2)	0.63	0.82	0.59	0.28

Table 17
Comparison of all ML techniques used across the performed tests.

RMSE [%]	Test description		Method			
	Test	Cycles [-]	SVR	GPR	FFNN	ANFIS
	Dataset Size Sensitivity (B1)	1/3 of dataset	0.30	0.29	0.24	0.47
		1/2 of dataset	0.18	0.19	0.37	0.20
		2/3 of dataset	0.20	0.18	0.29	0.13
	Dataset Size Sensitivity (B2)	1/3 of dataset	0.21	0.43	0.21	0.48
		1/2 of dataset	0.14	0.35	0.15	0.4
		2/3 of dataset	0.14	0.15	0.15	0.15
	Overfitting evaluation (B1)	1/2 of dataset	0.19	0.56	0.48	0.81
	Cross-battery validation, (B2 on B1 model)	580 (B1)	0.59	0.60	0.61	0.62
	Fine-tuning test, (B2 on B1 model)	350 (B1), 50 (B2)	0.45	0.45	0.39	0.51
	Cross-battery validation, (B1 on B2 model)	580 (B2)	0.57	0.61	0.60	0.61
	Fine-tuning test, (B1 on B2 model)	350 (B2), 50 (B1)	0.40	0.43	0.42	0.42
	Prismatic cell evaluation	1/2 of dataset	0.63	0.82	0.59	0.28

5. Conclusion

In this research, four data-driven methods, commonly referred to as ML techniques, were compared, each offering a unique approach to estimating the SOH of Samsung INR18650–35E Li-ion batteries, which were cycled under laboratory-controlled conditions using the CCCV method. To further extend the analysis and assess the generalization

capabilities of the models, an additional dataset of prismatic Li-ion batteries was incorporated, allowing for cross-validation on a different batteries.

Among the deterministic methods, SVR demonstrated stable performance across various dataset lengths, particularly in the overfitting tests. All features were used except for $t_{Tpeak(ch)}$, which exhibited significant noise, leading to an RMSE of 0.19%. In addition, SVR performed

best in the B2 prediction based on B1 data, although all methods produced nearly identical results due to the vector deviation in the second half of the SOH estimation.

In the ANN category, FFNN performed exceptionally well in predicting SOH for B2 using B1 data, particularly when fine-tuning with 50 cycles from B2. With an RMSE of 0.39 %, this technique successfully predicted the remaining 530 cycles of the second battery.

The ANFIS method, also falling under the ANN category, required input selection based on ES due to its inherent variability. This method performed best when 2/3 of the dataset was used for training, although it showed the weakest results in overfitting tests. ANFIS exhibited significant variability in RMSE when the number of training cycles changed, with strong results below 0.50 % RMSE for smaller datasets. However, between 1/3 and 1/2 of the dataset, RMSE increased sharply by a factor of 30, highlighting the method's sensitivity to certain input combinations that performed better in other contexts.

In contrast, the GPR method, representing probabilistic techniques, showed similar RMSE trends to ANFIS, despite being a fundamentally different approach. RMSE in GPR increased rapidly with the size of the training dataset, but unlike ANFIS, it remained significantly more stable and resistant to overfitting.

Each method presents distinct advantages and challenges. ANFIS demonstrated high accuracy but requires careful input selection due to its variability. FFNN showed stable RMSE in specific scenarios and proved effective in uncovering hidden patterns, as demonstrated in the SOH estimation for the second battery using fine-tuning. SVR, on the other hand, was the most stable method, offering reliable results across all SOH prediction tasks, including the challenge of overfitting. The overarching goal of achieving SOH estimation accuracy below 0.50 % was accomplished in nearly all cases, with the exception of SOH estimation for the second battery based solely on B1 data. Even this target can be met with simple ML methods like SVR.

Each method has its place in SOH estimation, depending on the specific requirements of accuracy, stability and dataset conditions. In addition to traditional approaches commonly used in this field, the research explores unique methods such as ANFIS, which is rarely applied in SOH prediction. Experimental results show that ANFIS can achieve excellent performance, provided the input features are selected appropriately. The experiments also revealed the limitations of individual methods, highlighting areas where others may excel. This study demonstrates that careful selection of methods and effective feature engineering can achieve high accuracy in SOH prediction, paving the way for practical real-world applications.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Marek Sedlářik: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Petr Vyroubal:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Dominika Capková:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Edin Omerdic:** Supervision, Conceptualization. **Mitchell Rae:** Writing – review & editing, Conceptualization. **Martin Mačák:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Martin Šedina:** Data curation. **Tomáš Kazda:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Data curation.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Petr Vyroubal reports financial support was provided by Brno University of Technology. Tomas Kazda reports financial support was provided by Brno University of Technology. Dominika Capkova reports financial

support was provided by University of Limerick. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

This publication was supported by the project "The Energy Conversion and Storage", funded as project No. CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004617 by Programme Johannes Amos Comenius, call Excellent Research. Support was also provided by the BUT specific research programme (project No. FEKT S 23–8286). D.C. acknowledges the EU Horizon 2023 research and innovation program under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Postdoctoral Fellowship Grant no. 101152715 (SALSA project).

Data Availability

The data that has been used is confidential.

References

- [1] P. Keil, S.F. Schuster, J. Wilhelm, J. Travi, A. Hauser, R.C. Karl, A. Jossen, Calendar Aging of Lithium-Ion Batteries, *J. Electrochem. Soc.* 163 (9) (2016) A1872–A1880. Jul.
- [2] I. Bloom, B.W. Cole, J.J. Sohn, S.A. Jones, E.G. Polzin, V.S. Battaglia, G. L. Henriksen, C. Motloch, R. Richardson, T. Unkelhaeuser, D. Ingersoll, H.L. Case, An accelerated calendar and cycle life study of Li-ion cells, *J. Power. Sources.* 101 (2) (2001) 238–247.
- [3] C.R. Birkl, M.R. Roberts, E. McTurk, P.G. Bruce, D.A. Howey, Degradation diagnostics for lithium ion cells, *J. Power. Sources.* 341 (2017) 373–386.
- [4] X. Ren, T. Sun, S. Mao, Y. Zheng, X. Han, M. Ouyang, Accelerated aging protocols design for Li-ion batteries based on equivalence of the degradation mechanisms, *J. Energy Storage* 99 (2024).
- [5] S. Nyamathulla, C. Dhanamjayulu, A review of battery energy storage systems and advanced battery management system for different applications: Challenges and recommendations, *J. Energy Storage* 86 (2024).
- [6] X. Hu, Y. Che, X. Lin, S. Onori, Battery Health Prediction Using Fusion-Based Feature Selection and Machine Learning, *IEEE Transactions on Transportation Electrification* 7 (2) (2021) 382–398.
- [7] P. Eleftheriadis, M. Gangi, S. Leva, A.V. Rey, E. Groppo, L. Grande, Comparative study of machine learning techniques for the state of health estimation of Li-ion batteries, *Electric Power Systems Research* 235 (9) (2024).
- [8] M. Zheng, X. Luo, Joint estimation of State of Charge (SOC) and State of Health (SOH) for lithium ion batteries using Support Vector Machine (SVM), Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) and Long Short Term Memory Network (LSTM) models, *Int. J. Electrochem. Sci.* 19 (9) (2024).
- [9] T.F. Fuller, M. Doyle, J. Newman, Simulation and Optimization of the Dual Lithium Ion Insertion Cell, *J. Electrochem. Soc.* 141 (1) (1994) 1–10. Jan.
- [10] P. Raj, E. Richter, F. Herb, J. Kempf, F. Michel, K.P. Birke, Electrochemical and aging model of li-ion batteries and estimation of total number of cycles during the lifecycle of the battery", *E-Prime - Advances in Electrical Engineering, Electronics and Energy* 9 (2024).
- [11] S. Han, Y. Tang, S. Khaleghi Rahimian, A numerically efficient method of solving the full-order pseudo-2-dimensional (P2D) Li-ion cell model, *J. Power. Sources.* 490 (2021).
- [12] P. Hashemzadeh, M. Désilets, M. Lacroix, A. Jokar, Investigation of the P2D and of the modified single-particle models for predicting the nonlinear behavior of Li-ion batteries, *J. Energy Storage* 52 (2022).
- [13] A. Hentunen, T. Lehmuspelto, J. Suomela, Time-Domain Parameter Extraction Method for Thévenin-Equivalent Circuit Battery Models, *IEEE Transactions on Energy Conversion* 29 (3) (2014) 558–566.
- [14] J. Wang, Y. Jia, N. Yang, Y. Lu, M. Shi, X. Ren, D. Lu, Precise equivalent circuit model for Li-ion battery by experimental improvement and parameter optimization, *J. Energy Storage* 52 (2022).
- [15] J. Park, Y. Jin, W. Kam, S. Han, A practical semi-empirical model for predicting the SoH of lithium-ion battery: a novel perspective on short-term rest, *J. Energy Storage* 96 (2024).
- [16] Z. -H. Zhou and S. Liu, *Machine Learning*. Singapore: Springer, 2021.
- [17] S. Khaleghi, M.S. Hosen, J. Van Mierlo, M. Berecibar, Towards machine-learning driven prognostics and health management of Li-ion batteries. A comprehensive review, *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 192 (2024).
- [18] X. Sui, S. He, S.B. Vilsen, J. Meng, R. Teodorescu, D.-I. Stroe, A review of non-probabilistic machine learning-based state of health estimation techniques for Lithium-ion battery, *Appl. Energy* 300 (2021).
- [19] Datong Liu, Wei Xie, Haitao Liao, Yu Peng, An Integrated Probabilistic Approach to Lithium-Ion Battery Remaining Useful Life Estimation, *IEEe Trans. Instrum. Meas.* 64 (3) (2015) 660–670.

- [20] H. Pan, Z. Lü, H. Wang, H. Wei, L. Chen, Novel battery state-of-health online estimation method using multiple health indicators and an extreme learning machine, *Energy* 160 (2018) 466–477.
- [21] J. Tian, R. Xiong, W. Shen, State-of-Health Estimation Based on Differential Temperature for Lithium Ion Batteries, *IEEE Trans. Power. Electron.* 35 (10) (2020) 10363–10373.
- [22] Y. Choi, S. Ryu, K. Park, H. Kim, Machine Learning-Based Lithium-Ion Battery Capacity Estimation Exploiting Multi-Channel Charging Profiles, *IEEE Access.* 7 (2019) 75143–75152.
- [23] H. Xu, L. Wu, S. Xiong, W. Li, A. Garg, L. Gao, An improved CNN-LSTM model-based state-of-health estimation approach for lithium-ion batteries, *Energy* 276 (2023).
- [24] V. Klass, M. Behm, G. Lindbergh, A support vector machine-based state-of-health estimation method for lithium-ion batteries under electric vehicle operation, *J. Power. Sources.* 270 (2014) 262–272.
- [25] X. Feng, C. Weng, X. He, X. Han, L. Lu, D. Ren, M. Ouyang, Online State-of-Health Estimation for Li-Ion Battery Using Partial Charging Segment Based on Support Vector Machine, *IEEE Trans. Veh. Technol.* 68 (9) (2019) 8583–8592.
- [26] A.G. Kashkooli, H. Fathiannasab, Z. Mao, Z. Chen, Application of Artificial Intelligence to State-of-Charge and State-of-Health Estimation of Calendar-Aged Lithium-Ion Pouch Cells, *J. Electrochem. Soc.* 166 (4) (2019) A605–A615. Feb.
- [27] S. Zhang, B. Zhai, X. Guo, K. Wang, N. Peng, X. Zhang, Synchronous estimation of state of health and remaining useful lifetime for lithium-ion battery using the incremental capacity and artificial neural networks, *J. Energy Storage* 26 (2019).
- [28] D. Andre, A. Nuhic, T. Soczka-Guth, D.U. Sauer, Comparative study of a structured neural network and an extended Kalman filter for state of health determination of lithium-ion batteries in hybrid electricvehicles, *Eng. Appl. Artif. Intell.* 26 (3) (2013) 951–961.
- [29] A.G. Olabi, A.A. Abdelghafar, B. Soudan, A.H. Alami, C. Semeraro, M. Al Radi, M. Al-Murisi, M.A. Abdelkareem, Artificial neural network driven prognosis and estimation of Lithium-Ion battery states: Current insights and future perspectives, *Ain Shams Engineering Journal* 15 (2) (2024).
- [30] P. Khumprom, N. Yodo, A Data-Driven Predictive Prognostic Model for Lithium-ion Batteries based on a Deep Learning Algorithm, *Energies. (Basel)* 12 (4) (2019).
- [31] Y. Wu, Q. Xue, J. Shen, Z. Lei, Z. Chen, Y. Liu, State of Health Estimation for Lithium-Ion Batteries Based on Healthy Features and Long Short-Term Memory, *IEEE Access.* 8 (2020) 28533–28547.
- [32] J. Wu, C. Zhang, Z. Chen, An online method for lithium-ion battery remaining useful life estimation using importance sampling and neural networks, *Appl. Energy* 173 (2016) 134–140.
- [33] L. Xing, X. Liu, W. Luo, L. Wu, State of Health Estimation for Lithium-Ion Batteries Using IAO-SVR, *World Electric Vehicle Journal* 14 (5) (2023).
- [34] Q. Li, D. Li, K. Zhao, L. Wang, K. Wang, State of health estimation of lithium-ion battery based on improved ant lion optimization and support vector regression, *J. Energy Storage* 50 (2022).
- [35] R.R. Richardson, M.A. Osborne, D.A. Howey, Gaussian process regression for forecasting battery state of health, *J. Power. Sources.* 357 (2017) 209–219.
- [36] K.P. Murphy, *Machine learning: a Probabilistic Perspective*. Cambridge: MIT Press, c 2012.
- [37] D.Y. Reddy, B. Routh, A. Patra, and S. Mukhopadhyay, “Gaussian Process Regression based State of Health Estimation of Lithium-Ion Batteries using Indirect Battery Health Indicators”, *2021 IEEE International Conference on Prognostics and Health Management (ICPHM)*, pp. 1–7, Jun. 2021.
- [38] J. Wang, Z. Deng, T. Yu, A. Yoshida, L. Xu, G. Guan, A. Abudula, State of health estimation based on modified Gaussian process regression for lithium-ion batteries, *J. Energy Storage* 51 (2022).
- [39] M.H. Sulaiman, Z. Mustafa, S. Razali, M.R. Daud, Advancing battery state of charge estimation in electric vehicles through deep learning: a comprehensive study using real-world driving data, *Cleaner Energy Systems* 8 (2024).
- [40] T. Takagi, M. Sugeno, Fuzzy identification of systems and its applications to modeling and control, *IEEE Trans. Syst. Man Cybern.* 15 (1) (1985) 116–132. SMC.
- [41] M.S. Zaghoul, R.A. Hamza, O.T. Iorhemen, J.H. Tay, Comparison of adaptive neuro-fuzzy inference systems (ANFIS) and support vector regression (SVR) for data-driven modelling of aerobic granular sludge reactors, *J. Environ. Chem. Eng.* 8 (3) (2020).
- [42] J. -S.R. Jang, C. -T. Sun, and E. Mizutani, *Neuro-Fuzzy and Soft Computing: a Computational Approach to Learning and Machine Intelligence*. Upper Saddle River: Prentice-Hall, 1997.
- [43] H. Meng, M. Geng, J. Xing, E. Zio, A hybrid method for prognostics of lithium-ion batteries capacity considering regeneration phenomena, *Energy* 261 (2022).
- [44] Y. Che, Z. Deng, X. Lin, L. Hu, X. Hu, Predictive Battery Health Management With Transfer Learning and Online Model Correction, *IEEE Trans. Veh. Technol.* 70 (2) (2021) 1269–1277.
- [45] Y. Che, D.-I. Stroe, X. Hu, R. Teodorescu, Semi-Supervised Self-Learning-Based Lifetime Prediction for Batteries, *IEEE Trans. Industr. Inform.* 19 (5) (2023) 6471–6481.
- [46] Y. Jiang, Y. Chen, F. Yang, W. Peng, State of health estimation of lithium-ion battery with automatic feature extraction and self-attention learning mechanism, *J. Power. Sources.* 556 (2023).
- [47] X. Shu, G. Li, J. Shen, Z. Lei, Z. Chen, Y. Liu, A uniform estimation framework for state of health of lithium-ion batteries considering feature extraction and parameters optimization, *Energy* 204 (2020).
- [48] X. Hou, X. Guo, Y. Yuan, K. Zhao, L. Tong, C. Yuan, L. Teng, The state of health prediction of Li-ion batteries based on an improved extreme learning machine, *J. Energy Storage* 70 (2023).
- [49] O. Klvac, J. Bana, Z. Stravova, K.Bouzek Stubianova, Dataset for "Study of Rapid Capacity Fade in Prismatic Li-ion Cells with Flexible Packaging, Zenodo (2024).
- [50] Z. Stravova, O. Klvac, J. Bana, B. Anothumakkool, T. Zikmund, P. Blazek, J. Kaiser, T. Kazda, Comprehensive study of rapid capacity fade in prismatic Li-ion cells with flexible packaging, *Sci. Rep.* 14 (1) (2024).